

Examining the Roles of Teacher and Caregiver Training in AAC-Supported Literacy Development for Children: A Systematic Literature Review

Paige Wilson

SAERA. School of Advanced Education Research and Accreditation

ABSTRACT

This systematic literature review investigates the role of teacher and caregiver training in augmentative and alternative communication (AAC)-assisted literacy development in children with complex communication needs (CCN). The aim was to discover whether communication partner training improved children's reading proficiency and skill generalization. Eligible studies were peer-reviewed articles published in English between 2005 and 2025 that focused on participants from birth to 18 and reported literacy or communication outcomes. A comprehensive search was carried out in PubMed, ERIC, and Taylor & Francis, with the most recent revision in 2025. Quality was assessed using Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) techniques, and findings were synthesized narratively. From 5,631 records, 45 studies met the inclusion criteria. Participants ranged from toddlers to adolescents, with interventions using low-to high-tech AAC systems. Results showed that training teachers and caregivers enhanced literacy abilities, vocabulary, reading comprehension, and symbolic communication. AAC interventions were most effective when paired with partner training. This review received no external funding and is not registered.

Keywords: *Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC); Literacy Development; Teacher Training; Caregiver Training; Communication Partners; Complex Communication Needs (CCN); Reading Proficiency; Systematic Literature Review*

INTRODUCTION

Background

Literacy is fundamental to academic success, social participation, and independence as an individual (Barker et al., 2013). Reading and writing provide a gateway to education, self-expression, and world navigation (Barker et al., 2013). This fundamental right is especially important for children with complex communication needs (CCN), for whom reading can be the primary way of developing novel, independent communication skills (Light et al., 2019).

Augmentative and Alternative Communication systems (AACs), which include both unassisted methods such as sign language and aided tools ranging from picture boards to high-tech speech-generating systems (Lorang et al., 2023), provide an essential link for these children. Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) gives learners the tools they need to access the curriculum, enhance their language skills, and participate meaningfully in social and academic settings.

AAC and literacy development

The potential for AAC to support literacy development is well-established in the research literature (Binger et al., 2008; Caron et al., 2023; Holyfield et al., 2025). Studies show that AAC interventions can help with not only communication but also emergent literacy abilities, including phonological awareness and letter-sound correspondence (Caron et al., 2023; Holyfield et al., 2025). Actively engaging in shared storybook reading along with other literacy activities, when combined with AAC devices, is very beneficial to literacy development (Binger et al., 2008; Cox et al., 2015). Despite this

potential, many individuals who use AAC still struggle to develop standard reading skills, with few reaching or exceeding the first-grade level (Benson-Goldberg & Erickson, 2024).

The role of communication partners

The effectiveness of AAC interventions is not determined by the technology alone, but rather by the quality of its implementation by skilled communication partners. Teachers and caregivers are the primary communicators who model language, provide opportunities, and use instructional strategies in everyday situations (Douglas, 2012; Kent-Walsh et al., 2010). However, if they are not sufficiently trained, they could unintentionally limit opportunities by using closed questioning, anticipating needs, or using AAC techniques inconsistently (Andzik et al., 2017; Douglas, 2012).

Evidence shows that systematic training may change this pattern. A meta-analysis found that communication partner education is highly successful at enhancing AAC user outcomes and emphasizing the importance of skilled teachers and caregivers (Kent-Walsh et al., 2015). Other research has shown that when caregivers or teachers are coached or educated, children demonstrate stronger symbolic communication, increased AAC use during literacy tasks, and improved reading comprehension and vocabulary (Brady et al., 2014; Conroy et al., 2019; Didion et al., 2019; Gormley et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, limitations such as minimal professional development, inadequate collaboration time, and a lack of accessible methods for training persist (Tremolada et al., 2022; Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024).

Gaps in existing research

Although individual studies have investigated AAC-supported literacy interventions, the evidence on how teacher and caregiver training affects children's reading outcomes remains scattered (Crowe et al., 2021; Douglas, 2012; Walker & Snell, 2013). Previous reviews have focused on AAC in literacy more broadly (Binger et al., 2008; Costantino & Bonati, 2014; Crowe et al., 2021; Kent-Walsh et al., 2015; Walker & Snell, 2013) and partner training in general communication skills (Douglas, 2012; Kent-Walsh & McNaughton, 2005; Parsons et al., 2017; Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024), but no known systematic review has rigorously studied the relationship between the two. For example, Douglas (2012) emphasized the importance of communication partners in modelling language and implementing instructional strategies, whereas Walker and Snell's (2013) meta-analysis highlighted methodological limitations in broader AAC research, such as a lack of studies measuring skill generalization and intervention consistency. However, a comprehensive review of how educating these significant partners affects AAC-supported literacy outcomes remains a critical gap in the literature. Given the increasing emphasis on inclusive education and family-centred interventions, analyzing this body of research is critical for shaping practice and policy (Kent-Walsh et al., 2015; Crowe et al., 2021; Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024; Parsons et al., 2017).

Objectives and hypotheses

Three objectives serve as the framework for this systematic review's efforts to address this gap. The first objective is to thoroughly analyze and synthesize the literature on the

effects of Augmentative and Alternative Communication systems on children's reading proficiency. The next objective is to determine if training teachers and caregivers in AAC-supported literacy practices enhances children's reading performance, along with skill generalization. The third aim is to identify critical AAC-supported literacy practices that contribute to long-term reading growth when implemented by trained communication partners.

Based upon these objectives, it is hypothesized that children whose teachers or caregivers receive training in AAC-supported literacy practices will demonstrate higher reading proficiency and better generalization of skills compared to those whose communication partners do not receive such training.

METHOD

Aim of the study

This study aims to perform a systematic literature review in order to investigate the effects of Augmentative and Alternative Communication interventions on children's reading outcomes. The primary objective is to determine whether reading performance is enhanced when teachers and/or caregivers receive training in AAC-supported literacy practices.

Eligibility criteria

The purpose of the inclusion criteria was to ensure that articles clearly relevant to the declared research question were selected. Articles were only chosen if they were written in English and published between 2005 and 2025. Eligible studies needed to focus on children within the age range of birth to 18 years. The research had to either

include teacher and/or caregiver training as part of the intervention or identify this training as a gap in the literature. Additionally, the studies were required to report findings related to communication and/or reading proficiency.

To narrow down the search and eliminate studies that were not relevant, exclusion criteria were utilized. Articles that primarily targeted adult populations were disqualified. Studies that did not include findings concerning both children and/or students and their teachers, caregivers, or professionals were excluded. Furthermore, articles without results relating to communication and/or reading proficiency were rejected. Studies were excluded if they lacked a relevant AAC focus or contained no data regarding AAC. Opinion pieces and abstract conferences were excluded. If the full text of the article was not available, it was not considered. Only journals that were written by human authors, rather than artificial intelligence (AI), were included. Lastly, articles published outside of the designated publishing range (2005-2025) or written in languages other than English were not included.

Information sources and search strategy

A systematic search was conducted across three databases: PubMed, ERIC, and Taylor & Francis. The three steps of the search method were title screening, abstract assessment, and full-text analysis. Criteria for inclusion and exclusion were used at each step to narrow down the selection of articles. Filters and keywords were applied to refine results for each database.

The literature search was first conducted using the scholarly database PubMed. Relevant studies were retrieved using a set of

keywords and Boolean operators, such as (Parent OR Partner OR Teacher OR Children) AND Communication AND (AAC OR Augmentative Alternative Communication). The search was filtered to include articles published between 2005 and 2025, written in English, with free full text available, human participants, and an age range of birth to 18 years. This search yielded 170 results, of which 22 were included in the final review.

The next academic database utilized was ERIC. On this database, the search was limited using the filters of peer-reviewed only, published since 2005, full text availability, and the publication type of journal articles. Relevant studies were retrieved using a set of keywords and Boolean operators, such as (AAC OR Augmentative and Alternative Communication) AND (Students OR Individuals) AND (Communication OR Literacy) AND (Caregiver OR Teacher OR Educator). This search yielded 155 results, of which 7 were included in the final review.

The third database that was used for this procedure was Taylor & Francis. The search was filtered for articles published since 2005 in English. Relevant studies were retrieved using a set of keywords and Boolean operators, such as (AAC OR Augmentative and Alternative Communication OR Communication Partner) AND (Literacy OR Reading OR Reading Outcomes) AND (Child OR Children OR Student OR Students) AND (Instruction OR Intervention OR Training OR Support). Of the three used for this systematic literature review, Taylor & Francis generated the highest number of results. The search conducted on this database yielded 5,306 results, of which 16 were included in the final review.

Following the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria, 45 articles were selected for the systematic review. The articles that were chosen had proven to be reliable, relevant, and in accordance with the research topic due to the above systematic technique.

Selection process

Upon the removal of 235 duplicates, 5,396 files remained for screening. 4,862 articles were excluded after having been examined for titles and abstracts. Of the 534 reports considered for retrieval, 128 were not found. The remaining 406 reports were evaluated in full text. Reports were rejected due to a lack of findings on both adults and children ($n = 58$), an irrelevant AAC focus ($n = 287$), no data reported for AAC users ($n = 15$), or a retraction ($n = 1$). The final review consisted of 45 studies. A Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow chart was developed to illustrate the selection process (see Annex A, Figure 1). A single reviewer screened all titles, abstracts, and full texts. While this technique provided consistency, it also introduced a limitation in that independent verification by numerous reviewers may have reduced the possibility of selection bias.

Data collection and data items

The data was extracted manually by a single researcher. The information gathered included the study design, sample size, participant age range, nature of the AAC system, and the role of educators and/or caregivers in the intervention. Interest objectives included children's reading proficiency, communication outcomes, and the generalization of literacy-related skills. No automation techniques were utilized, and no assumptions were made when information was unclear or unavailable.

Effect measures

Given that no meta-analysis had been conducted, statistical effect measures were not used in this review. Rather, the results were narratively synthesized. The narrative synthesis aimed to identify patterns and themes regarding the impact of teacher and caregiver training on children's communication and literacy outcomes. This approach was deemed appropriate since the included studies consistently provided qualitative descriptions of the objectives being sought, such as reading competency, communication development, and literacy skill generalization.

Risk of bias assessment

Seeing as the selected studies included multiple study design types, the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal tools were utilized. JBI was chosen over other tools to improve the construct validity and replicability of assessments. The techniques that were used included analytical cross-sectional studies, quasi-experimental (non-randomized) studies, cohort studies (Moola et al., 2020), case series, case reports, qualitative research (Lockwood et al., 2015), systematic reviews/research syntheses, and textual/narrative evidence for conceptual and policy papers (McArthur et al., 2020). There were no randomized controlled trials included. Thus, the RoB-2 technique was not applied. For mixed-methods research, each methodological component was assessed using the appropriate JBI assessment tool. As a result, some studies appear in multiple design-specific visuals but are only counted once in the synthesis (45 distinct studies, 49 assessments displayed due to four mixed-methods studies). For the sake of consistency, the JBI checklists were tested on three studies

to confirm the coding criteria for “Yes,” “No,” “Unclear,” or “N/A.” From there, all included studies were evaluated using the appropriate checklist for their design. Items marked “N/A” were removed from the denominators, and quick data notes were made for transparency. Heatmaps were implemented to represent item-level assessments together with an average score across checklist items to help with understanding. “Yes” was coded as 1.0, “No” as 0.0, “Unclear” as 0.5, and “Partial” as 0.75. The scores were divided into four categories: high (≥ 0.85), moderate (0.70-0.84), low (0.50-0.69), and critically low (< 0.50). These scores were solely used as a visual guide; they did not replace item-level assessments. No study was removed purely because of the risk of bias. However, the assessment results determined how much weight was placed on specific study results, how confounding and cause-and-effect timing were addressed, and the overall confidence in the conclusions.

Synthesis methods

The research articles included ($n = 45$) were synthesized narratively. The studies were systematically classified according to whether they contained caregiver training, teacher training, both, or defined training as a gap in the literature. There were no data conversions required, but the language was standardized (for example, ‘caregiver’ was used to encompass terms including ‘parent’ along with ‘communication partner’). Tables were used to present study features and outcomes, which were then narratively described. The findings were interpreted based on the methodological quality of the research, which was assessed using the JBI critical appraisal procedures. A meta-analysis was not performed due to heterogeneity in study designs and outcome measures.

Instead, narrative synthesis was used to discover patterns and themes in the literature. To account for heterogeneity, differences between studies were noted. This included variations in AAC type, intervention format, and participant characteristics. No sensitivity analyses were carried out.

Reporting bias assessment

Reporting bias was evaluated narratively. This was to identify selective outcome reporting and contradictions between techniques and findings. Some studies did not provide all of the intervention effects, communication outcomes, or literacy results, suggesting that selective reporting may have occurred. Given that this was a narrative review and not a meta-analysis, statistical measures for reporting bias were not applicable.

Certainty assessment

The certainty of evidence was assessed using the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluations (GRADE) criteria carried out narratively (Guyatt et al., 2008). The risk of bias (as assessed by JBI), consistency of results across studies, directness of populations and interventions, precision of effect estimates (sample size and reporting details), as well as potential publication bias were all taken into account. The key findings were characterized as having high, moderate, low, or very low certainty. Larger sample sizes, explicit intervention descriptions, and consistent outcome reporting increased certainty, whereas small sample sizes, unclear reporting, and methodological issues decreased certainty.

RESULTS

Study selection

A systematic search throughout PubMed, ERIC, and Taylor & Francis generated 5,631 results. After removing 235 duplicates, 5,396 articles remained for screening. After scanning the titles and abstracts, 4,862 publications were eliminated because they failed to satisfy the inclusion criteria. A total of 534 full-text articles were retrieved and reviewed; however, 128 could not be accessed. Of the 406 full-text publications assessed, 361 were removed for the following reasons: irrelevant AAC focus ($n = 287$), lack of findings about children and their adult communication partners ($n = 58$), no AAC outcome data ($n = 15$), or retraction ($n = 1$). The final narrative synthesis consisted of 45 studies. The study selection procedure is illustrated in Annex A (Figure 1, PRISMA Flow Diagram). There were no studies removed purely because of methodological flaws or the risk of bias.

Study characteristics

The 45 included studies varied in design, including quasi-experimental interventions (e.g., Conroy, Kaiser, & Ledford, 2019), cross-sectional surveys (e.g., Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024), mixed-methods approaches (e.g., Gormley, Light, & Barkmeier-Kraemer, 2020), qualitative interviews (e.g., Andzik, Chung, Doneski-Nicol, & Dollarhide, 2018), and case studies (e.g., Caron, Ryan, Babb, Holyfield, & O'Brien, 2023). No randomized controlled trials were found.

The participants' ages ranged from toddlers to adolescents (birth to 18 years), reflecting a collection of studies that involve treatment methods for young children (Branson & Demchak, 2011). Sample sizes ranged from

single-case treatments (Caron et al., 2023; Holyfield et al., 2025) to large survey studies with over 200 participants (Crowe, Machalicek, Wei, Drew, & Ganz, 2021).

The AAC systems studied ranged from unaided sign language (Holmer, Heimann, & Rudner, 2017) to low-tech picture-based systems (Binger et al., 2008) to high-tech eye-gaze speech-generating devices (Caron et al., 2023; Holyfield et al., 2025). Interventions often included structured literacy tools, including dialogic reading, aided language modelling, and systematic prompting, along with communication partner training. They also included innovative methods like serious games and immersive communication settings (Serret et al., 2017; van der Schuit et al., 2010).

Teacher-focused research frequently looked at perceptions of AAC use in schools (Andzik et al., 2018; Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024; Lorang et al., 2023), whereas caregiver-focused studies emphasized coaching in shared reading as well as daily routines (Binger et al., 2008; Fäldt et al., 2019; Tremolada et al., 2022).

Study designs, participant characteristics, AAC systems, and training emphases for all 45 studies are summarized in Annex B (Table 1). It addresses both the variety of AAC methods and the significance of teacher and caregiver training in shaping literacy outcomes.

Risk of bias in studies

The Joanna Briggs Institute Critical Appraisal Tools were used to assess the risk of bias. Overall, the methodological quality of the included studies was moderate to high.

Clear intervention descriptions (e.g., Kent-Walsh, Binger, & Hasham, 2010), validated outcome measures (e.g., phonological awareness, vocabulary, reading comprehension), as well as consistent application of intervention methods were among the strengths (e.g., Conroy et al., 2019; Caron et al., 2023). Limitations included small sample sizes (e.g., single-case reports such as Gormley et al., 2020), minimal follow-up data (e.g., Smith & Hustad, 2016), a lack of blinding, and the potential for reporting bias in qualitative studies (e.g., Douglas, 2012).

No studies were omitted because of the risk of bias, but these judgments influenced the weighting of evidence in the synthesis. Study-level JBI scores (0-1) and risk ratings are detailed in Annex D (Table 3). Visual appraisal summaries for each study design are provided in Annexes E-L (Figures 2-9). Analytical cross-sectional studies were generally rated as moderate quality, with average scores ranging from 0.71 to 0.79 (see Annex E, Figure 2). However, systematic reviews and meta-analyses were consistently of high quality, with the majority scoring above 0.90 in JBI appraisals (see Annex F, Figure 3). Case series studies were also of high overall quality, with some single-case literacy interventions scoring slightly lower (see Annex G, Figure 4). Similarly, case reports were scored highly for rigour, with both examples receiving 0.88 (see Annex H, Figure 5). The review's single cohort study received a moderate-quality rating of 0.72, with limitations due to confounding factors and follow-up issues (see Annex I, Figure 6). Quasi-experimental studies were consistently of high quality, with scores ranging from 0.94 to 0.97, indicating strong methodological design and reliable outcomes (see Annex K,

Figure 8). Narrative and conceptual works were also rated high quality due to their clear focus, logical argumentation, and relevance to AAC-supported literacy (see Annex J, Figure 7). Qualitative studies received high ratings (≥ 0.85), indicating strong trustworthiness, reflexivity, and methodological rigour across various study contexts (see Annex L, Figure 9). Collectively, these findings suggest that, while some study designs had moderate limitations, the overall body of evidence demonstrated high methodological quality. To reiterate, these assessments did not result in the exclusion of studies but rather served to guide the amount of weight given to individual findings in the synthesis, ensuring that stronger evidence contributed more heavily to the conclusions. Most studies achieved high quality (≥ 0.85), particularly single-case and quasi-experimental designs. Surveys and cohort studies were more frequently graded moderate. Narrative and conceptual articles were methodologically sound yet received a moderate-to-high rating due to their non-empirical design.

Results of individual studies

Across the 45 included studies, the results consistently showed that AAC interventions, especially when combined with teacher or caregiver training, improved reading and communication outcomes. Training methods were connected to improvements in emergent literacy skills, such as phonological awareness and letter-sound knowledge (Caron et al., 2023; Holyfield et al., 2025; Ulriksen et al., 2024). Caregiver coaching during shared storybook reading was linked to enhanced multi-symbol message use and growth in vocabulary (Binger et al., 2008; Kent-Walsh et al., 2010). Similarly, AAC-supported dialogic reading with trained

caregivers or educators improved both reading comprehension and narrative engagement (Almubark et al., 2025; Conroy et al., 2019; Quinn et al., 2020). Furthermore, multiple studies showed that skills developed in structured reading sessions translated to home and classroom settings, suggesting the larger impact of AAC-supported literacy interventions (Cox et al., 2015; Fäldt et al., 2019; Gona et al., 2014).

Results of syntheses

The included studies showed significant variability in AAC type, participant demographics, and training methodologies. The risk of bias was generally moderate to high, but consistent across designs.

A meta-analysis was ruled out due to the heterogeneity of the included studies. Thematic patterns across studies are organized in Annex C (Table 2). Communication partner instruction consistently enhanced child reading and communication outcomes, demonstrating the value of training in improving achievements (Kent-Walsh et al., 2015; Douglas, 2012). Parent-focused interventions during shared reading improved symbolic communication and engagement, suggesting the beneficial effects of caregiver coaching (Audrée et al., 2014; Binger et al., 2008; Fäldt et al., 2019; Finestack et al., 2022; Tremolada et al., 2022). Despite these strengths, teachers generally indicated a lack of training and confidence in AAC literacy methods, stressing the need for professional development (Andzik et al., 2018; Berenguer et al., 2022; Conlon et al., 2021; Lorang et al., 2023; Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024). Classroom-based research pointed out the importance of literacy opportunities, assistive technology integration, and stakeholder

engagement in determining outcomes (Benson-Goldberg & Erickson, 2024; Ibrahim et al., 2023; Nordström et al., 2019; Suhr et al., 2023; Uthoff et al., 2021). Finally, various reviews and case studies found that AAC therapies improved emotional communication, increased involvement, and reduced problematic behaviours (Roldán et al., 2021; Walker & Snell, 2013).

The majority of the variation in outcomes was accounted for by differences in intervention type, AAC modality, and participant age. For example, eye-gaze devices (Caron et al., 2023) required different supports than picture exchange systems (Binger et al., 2008).

No thorough sensitivity analyses were performed. However, single-case studies consistently confirmed larger-scale survey and review findings, enhancing confidence in the direction of effect.

Reporting biases

Some studies offered minimal reporting of outcome measures (for example, missing follow-up data and incomplete literacy evaluations). Selective reporting was suggested in some survey studies that stressed mainly positive features of teacher or caregiver perceptions (Andzik et al., 2018; Laubscher et al., 2024; Lund et al., 2017).

Certainty of evidence

Using GRADE criteria, the overall certainty of evidence was rated as moderate. The consistency of findings across multiple methodologies and populations increased certainty. The study's limitations were small sample sizes, limited longitudinal data, and methodological variation.

DISCUSSION

Interpretation of Results

This systematic literature review included 45 studies that investigated the impact of teacher and caregiver training on children's literacy development when implementing Augmentative and Alternative Communication. Overall, the results show that AAC interventions work best when combined with systematic training for communication partners. Coaching teachers and caregivers improved emergent literacy skills, reading comprehension, symbolic communication, as well as vocabulary development in a variety of settings (Binger et al., 2008; Caron et al., 2023; Conroy et al., 2019; Holyfield et al., 2025; Kent-Walsh et al., 2010).

Caregiver coaching during shared storybook reading frequently led to better vocabulary and multi-symbol message use (Binger et al., 2008; Kent-Walsh et al., 2010). Similarly, dialogic reading approaches with trained educators and caregivers improved reading comprehension, narrative engagement, and literacy skill generalization in both home and school contexts (Conroy et al., 2019; Quinn et al., 2020). Teacher-focused research found that systematic training raised awareness of AAC techniques as well as confidence in incorporating these strategies into classroom literacy instruction (Andzik et al., 2018; Lorang et al., 2023; Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024).

These findings are consistent with previous reviews emphasizing the relevance of communication partner training for overall AAC outcomes (Douglas, 2012; Kent-Walsh et al., 2015). However, this current synthesis narrows this lens by focusing on literacy, providing new perspectives into how partner

training directly affects reading results for children with complex communication needs.

Limitations of the Evidence

Although the results consistently supported the importance of teacher and caregiver training, the included studies had some limitations that should be addressed. First, no randomized controlled trials (RCTs) were found in the evidence base. Instead, the studies focused primarily on quasi-experimental methods, surveys, case studies, and qualitative research. While quasi-experimental designs were frequently assessed to be of high quality in the JBI assessment (Conroy et al., 2019; Quinn et al., 2020), other designs had fundamental methodological weaknesses.

Small sample sizes were common, especially in single-case study designs (Caron et al., 2023; Holyfield et al., 2025). Such studies provide valuable insights into individual outcomes but have limited generalizability. Several studies also reported limited follow-up, making it challenging to determine whether literacy gains persisted over time (Smith & Hustad, 2016). Furthermore, surveys and qualitative research, while methodologically thorough, were sensitive to self-report bias and selective reporting of favourable outcomes (Andzik et al., 2018).

Despite these limitations, the risk-of-bias analysis using JBI methods revealed that the majority of the included studies were of moderate to high quality, with quasi-experimental and qualitative designs receiving particularly high scores. Nonetheless, the heterogeneity in study design, sample characteristics, and intervention focus lowers the overall certainty of conclusions.

Limitations of the Review Process

Several limitations in the review process should also be discussed. First, the systematic search was restricted to three databases: PubMed, ERIC, and Taylor & Francis. Although these databases contain a significant amount of relevant AAC and education research, the exclusion of other databases (e.g., PsycINFO, Scopus) and grey literature raises the possibility that key studies may have been overlooked. Restricting inclusion to English-language publications between 2005 and 2025 increased the risk of language and publication bias.

Following that, data screening and extraction were conducted by a single reviewer, which, although assuring consistency, increased the potential of selection bias. Independent evaluation by several reviewers may have strengthened reliability. Furthermore, because of the significant variation in trial designs, outcome measures, and intervention forms, the review used narrative synthesis rather than meta-analyses. While narrative synthesis was appropriate, it limited the capacity to measure pooled effect sizes and carry out sensitivity analyses.

Moreover, while JBI appraisal measures were used systematically, their interpretation was subjective to some extent, as is prevalent in critical assessment methods (Barker et al., 2024; Munn et al., 2020).

Implications for Practice, Policy, and Future Research

The findings highlight the importance of communication partner training in enhancing the effectiveness of AAC-supported literacy interventions. Teachers and caregivers are the gatekeepers to literacy access, and without

sufficient training, AAC systems may be inadequately utilized or applied inconsistently. When integrated into everyday routines, practical techniques like dialogic reading, aided language modelling, and methodical prompting are extremely beneficial. Speech-language pathologists (SLPs) should focus on coaching initiatives that increase caregiver and teacher competency in such approaches (Kent-Walsh et al., 2010; Conroy et al., 2019).

From a policy standpoint, the study emphasizes the critical need for structured professional development opportunities in AAC literacy. Schools should devote resources to teacher training programs. Similarly, administrations should invest in easily accessible education efforts for families with CCN. Policies promoting inclusive education must also acknowledge that partner training is a necessary component of successful AAC implementation (McNaughton et al., 2019; Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024). Collaboration between the educational and healthcare communities ought to be required to maintain sustainability.

The findings of the study suggest multiple opportunities for future research. There is a dire need for rigorous RCTs and longitudinal studies that can establish connections between variables and assess the sustainability of literacy growth. Given that the majority of the studies covered were conducted in the United States or Western Europe, research should also consider cross-cultural contexts and characteristics such as participation and age in children with CCN. (Crowe et al., 2021; Raghavendra et al., 2007). Furthermore, future research should look at the transfer of literacy skills to real-world contexts, identify barriers to

implementation, and assess the cost-effectiveness of training programs (Light et al., 2019; Parsons et al., 2017).

Feasibility Plan of Action

To convert the review's findings into measurable steps, a comprehensive, feasible plan of action is provided. One major objective is to establish blended-learning training models that incorporate online courses, in-person workshops, and personalized coaching sessions for both educators and caregivers. These formats would make training more accessible and flexible to a variety of schedules and learning methods. Furthermore, AAC-supported literacy practices should be incorporated into both scheduled instruction in schools and informal family interactions. This would ensure that children have consistent chances to develop communication and literacy abilities across various settings. Such implementation would benefit from close collaboration across disciplines among speech-language pathologists, teachers, and families, leading to a unified support system.

Despite the potential benefits of these approaches, some obstacles must be overcome, including limited training opportunities, lack of time for educators and caregivers, and disparities in access to AAC technology. These barriers can be addressed by pushing for institutional support and policy changes that promote equitable access to AAC resources and professional development opportunities (Uthoff et al., 2021). Children with complex communication needs are more likely to attain significant improvements in reading proficiency, communication independence, and academic inclusion with consistent and

well-structured training (Benson-Goldberg & Erickson, 2024; Roldán et al., 2021).

Synthesis of Findings

In summary, this review reveals that teacher and caregiver training is crucial to the success of AAC-supported literacy initiatives. While methodological inconsistency and intrinsic constraints limit the evidence base, the findings provide moderate-certainty evidence that communication partner training improves reading outcomes for children with CCN. These findings have clear implications for practice, policy, and future research, highlighting the importance of systematic integration of training into AAC therapies.

CONCLUSIONS

Revisiting the Study Aim

The purpose of this systematic literature review was to explore the role of teacher and caregiver training in augmentative and alternative communication-based literacy interventions for children with complex communication needs. The rationale for this research stems from the recognition that children with CCN frequently encounter literacy development barriers, despite AAC systems' significant potential to support language acquisition, emergent literacy skills, and long-term reading growth (Light et al., 2019; Caron et al., 2023). While AAC technology and strategies serve as crucial tools, the literature shows that the effectiveness of such interventions is closely related to the competence and confidence of the communication partners who deliver them. These communication partners are typically teachers in educational settings and caregivers at home (Douglas, 2012; Kent-Walsh et al., 2015).

The initial goal of this review was to gather the evidence concerning how AAC interventions affect children's reading proficiency. The second goal was to investigate whether training for teachers and caregivers improves the results of these interventions. The third goal was to identify AAC-supported literacy practices that, when used by trained communication partners, promote long-term literacy development. As described below, this section assesses the review's success in achieving these aims, analyzes its contributions to knowledge, and highlights the significance of the findings for education, clinical practice, and future study.

Achievement of the Research Objectives

As mentioned, the first goal of this thesis was to examine and synthesize the literature on the effects of AAC interventions on children's literacy skills. This goal was accomplished by a systematic review of 45 studies that included quasi-experimental designs, mixed-methods research, cross-sectional surveys, case studies, and qualitative interviews. These studies discovered that AAC interventions, ranging from sign language and picture-based systems to high-tech eye-gaze devices, can help students develop emergent literacy skills like phonological awareness, vocabulary acquisition, and narrative engagement (Binger et al., 2008; Holyfield et al., 2025). The study offered an exhaustive summary of the current state of evidence by categorizing and narratively integrating these varied methods. It validated previous beliefs regarding AAC's ability to promote literacy while emphasizing the large variation in intervention methods, target populations, and literacy outcomes. The review indicates that AAC alone is insufficient. With this, success is determined by how well AAC use is incorporated into the

child's literacy environment, which is crucial to the second aim of the study.

The second aim was to evaluate whether educating communication partners improves reading outcomes for children who use AAC. This objective was also met adequately. The results from the included studies continually pointed to the value of formal training for teachers and caregivers. Studies in which caregivers were coached during shared storybook reading found significant gains in vocabulary use, message development, and symbolic communication (Kent-Walsh et al., 2010; Fäldt et al., 2019). Similarly, interventions that taught teachers in dialogic reading or supported language modelling resulted in increased reading comprehension and narrative engagement among children (Conroy et al., 2019; Quinn et al., 2020). The review supported the hypothesis that educating communication partners improves literacy outcomes compared to AAC therapies administered without training. However, it also revealed a recurring gap. The gap is that teachers regularly reported a lack of understanding, confidence, or institutional support when using AAC for literacy education (Andzik et al., 2018; Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024). This conclusion emphasizes the importance of systemic professional growth opportunities and aligns with broader requests to incorporate AAC training into both preservice teacher training and ongoing professional learning.

The third goal was to uncover specific AAC-supported literacy practices that promote long-term reading growth when practiced by skilled communication partners. This target was partially met. The review identified various beneficial strategies, such as dialogic reading, shared storybook reading, aided language modelling, and systematic

prompting (Binger et al., 2008; Conroy et al., 2019; Quinn et al., 2020). These methods frequently led to increases in emergent literacy and communication skills. However, there are still gaps in the literature on outcomes over time. Many of the included studies did not have lengthy follow-up periods, making it difficult to assess whether literacy skill improvements were sustained over time (Smith & Hustad, 2016). Similarly, while skill transfer to home and school settings has been observed in some cases (Cox et al., 2015), few studies have systematically assessed the maintenance of these skills after the intervention period. Future research is required to improve the evidence base for long-term literacy trajectories linked with AAC-supported training methods.

Together, the three objectives of this thesis were met appropriately. The review presented a clear synthesis of evidence, confirmed the importance of communication partner training, and outlined promising literacy practices while noting ongoing research limitations.

Contribution to Knowledge

This thesis contributes to the research and professional understanding of AAC-supported literacy development in multiple significant ways. First, it contributes to the field by providing a systematic review particularly focused on the connection of literacy outcomes and communication partner training in AAC contexts. Previous studies addressed AAC and literacy in a broader sense (Crowe et al., 2021; Walker & Snell, 2013) or examined partner training in relation to communication without emphasizing literacy (Douglas, 2012; Parsons et al., 2017). By bringing together

these two avenues of research, this thesis fills a significant knowledge gap and lays the groundwork for future research.

Secondly, the thesis promotes methodology by using Joanna Briggs Institute critical appraisal techniques for a variety of study designs, which are reinforced with GRADE assessments of certainty. This approach allowed for a deeper analysis of findings, ensuring that conclusions were based on the methodological quality of the included studies. The visualization of evaluation findings, presented as heatmaps and tables, offers transparency and replicability to other researchers conducting similar studies.

Thirdly, the thesis had practical implications for the design and execution of AAC therapies. The review identifies dialogic reading, caregiver coaching, and assisted language modelling as particularly beneficial techniques, providing clear guidance for clinicians, educators, and administrators seeking evidence-based strategies to improve literacy outcomes for children with CCN.

Significance for Practice and Policy

This thesis is directly relevant to practice and policy, in addition to its academic contribution. For those in the profession, the findings highlight that AAC interventions cannot be entirely effective without the active participation of trained communication partners. Teachers and caregivers must have not just the technical skills to use AAC systems, but also the pedagogical expertise to apply these tools into literacy-rich settings. Speech-language pathologists are well positioned to conduct this training, collaborating with families and educators to ensure consistent support across contexts.

For policymakers, the thesis stresses the critical need for institutional investment in AAC education and training. Schools should prioritize professional development opportunities that prepare teachers to conduct AAC-based literacy instruction, while governments and community organizations should create accessible caregiver education programs. Regulations like these must also address systemic obstacles such as unequal access to AAC technology and insufficient time for training within school schedules.

By considering these concerns, the thesis contributes to a global movement toward equitable literacy access for children with CCN (Light et al., 2019; McNaughton et al., 2019).

Fulfillment of the Research Aims

Overall, this thesis met its objectives by confirming that educating communication partners is critical to the success of AAC-supported literacy programs. Beyond validating the basic theory, the thesis contributed to a better understanding by identifying beneficial strategies, pointing out persistent limitations, and suggesting additional research opportunities. In doing so, it offered a comprehensive, evidence-based solution to the research challenges that inspired the study.

The thesis also highlighted important limits in both the evidence base and the review process, providing an understanding of methodological limitations while presenting meaningful findings. Importantly, the findings extend beyond academic theory and provide practical advice for practitioners, institutions, and policymakers. The Discussion's feasibility plan of action presents an outline for putting these results into practice, ensuring that children with

CCN across the globe benefit from AAC-supported literacy.

Concluding Reflections

In conclusion, this systematic study reveals that the success of AAC interventions in fostering literacy is dependent not only on the technology itself, but also on the quality of use by trained communication partners. Teachers and caregivers play critical roles in modelling, reinforcing, and extending literacy practices (Douglas, 2012; Kent-Walsh & McNaughton, 2005). Their training shows a direct impact on the academic success of children with CCN. The evidence presented here demonstrates that investing in communication partner training is not optional, but rather essential to inclusive, successful literacy instruction.

While obstacles still exist, such as the need for enhanced study designs, long-term outcome data, and systemic policy support, the evidence points in a clear direction. Training initiatives that prepare teachers and caregivers to conduct AAC-supported literacy interventions have the potential to improve the educational trajectories of children with CCN, allowing them to exercise their fundamental right to literacy (Kent-Walsh et al., 2015; Crowe et al., 2021).

To reiterate, this thesis therefore concludes not only that its aims were met, but also that its findings provide a significant contribution to the progress of research, practice, and policy in speech-language pathology and special education. This supports the overall message that literacy development for children with complex communication needs is feasible when technology is combined with personal commitment, competence, and collaboration.

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Annex A

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram of Study Selection

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram showing the study selection process.

Annex B

Table 1.

Characteristics of Included Studies (n = 45)

Author, Year	Country	Study Design	Sample (n, age)	AAC Type	Training Focus	Main Outcomes
Andzik et al., 2017	USA	Survey	52 teachers of students using AAC	Mixed AAC	Teachers	Teacher confidence correlated with training; highlighted ongoing PD needs
Andzik et al., 2018	USA	Qualitative interviews	14 special educators	Mixed AAC	Teachers	Barriers: inconsistent implementation, limited training; need for systematic PD
Conlon, Preston, & Zupan 2021	Australia	Mixed-methods survey	SLPs working in pediatrics (n = 200)	Mixed AAC	Teachers (SLP training)	SLPs reported inadequate AAC training at university; strong need for embedded, hands-on AAC literacy training.
Barker et al., 2013	USA	Narrative review	n/a	Mixed AAC	Gap	Design considerations for generalizable AAC literacy interventions
Benson-Goldberg & Erickson, 2024	USA	Mixed-methods (observational/survey)	26 classrooms (students with ESN/CCN)	Mixed AAC	Teachers	Limited literacy opportunities; AAC often underutilized during instruction
Binger et al., 2008	USA	Multiple-probe single-subject	3 parents + 3 children (2–6y)	Low-tech symbols	Caregivers	Parent coaching increased multi-symbol utterances during shared reading
Brady et al., 2014	USA	Longitudinal SEM	93 children using AAC	Mixed AAC	Gap (predictors)	Child symbolic skills + caregiver input predicted vocabulary growth
Branson & Demchak, 2011	USA	Systematic review	12 studies (birth–36 months)	Mixed AAC	Caregivers	Early AAC facilitated communication; called for more infant/toddler literacy research
Caron et al., 2023	USA	Single-case experimental	1 child with CP (8y)	Eye-gaze AAC	Teacher	Explicit literacy instruction improved letter–sound correspondence
Conroy et al., 2019	USA	Quasi-experimental	Preschoolers with Down	AAC modeling	Teachers	Dialogic reading + AAC modeling

Table 1 (continued)

Author, Year	Country	Study Design	Sample (n, age)	AAC Type	Training Focus	Main Outcomes
			syndrome (n = 12, 3–5y)			improved comprehension and AAC use
Crowe et al., 2021	USA	Mega-review	84 reviews covering AAC in IDD	Mixed AAC	Gap	Summarized evidence; identified methodological and implementation gaps
Cox et al., 2015	USA	Multiple-baseline across behaviors	3 dyads (7–13y, SSML)	Mixed (VOCA + symbols)	Caregivers	Shared reading with AAC increased communication; some generalization to routines
Douglas, 2012	USA	Literature review	n/a	Mixed AAC	Paraeducators (Teachers)	Strategy-based partner training improves AAC interactions; implementation guidance
Fäldt et al., 2019	Sweden	Qualitative (parent perception)	Parents of toddlers in early AAC-focused intervention	Mixed AAC	Caregivers	Parents reported increased engagement and carryover following coaching
Gormley et al., 2020	USA	Mixed-methods pilot	1 child + parent + provider in inpatient rehab	High-tech AAC	Both	Parent–child–provider AAC interactions improved with structured coaching
Holyfield et al., 2025	USA	Single-case experimental	4 emerging communicators (3–6y)	High-tech AAC with embedded literacy	Teachers	Embedded literacy supports increased participation during shared reading
Holmer et al., 2017	Sweden	Crossover experimental	DHH children (n = 30, 6–12y)	Computerized sign-based literacy	Gap	Sign-based computerized training improved word reading and literacy
Ibrahim et al., 2023	UK	Ethnographic qualitative	Primary classrooms (children using AAC + staff)	Mixed AAC	Teachers	Classroom interaction shaped by AAC; highlighted teacher role in scaffolding
Kent-Walsh & McNaughton, 2005	USA	Literature review	n/a	Mixed AAC	Gap	Proposed Communication Partner Instruction model; guided future AAC training studies
Kent-Walsh, Binger, & Hasham, 2010	USA	Multiple-probe single-subject	3 parents + 3 children (3–7y)	Low-tech AAC	Caregivers	Parent training increased symbolic communication during storybook reading

Table 1 (continued)

Author, Year	Country	Study Design	Sample (n, age)	AAC Type	Training Focus	Main Outcomes
Kent-Walsh, Murza, Malani, & Binger, 2015	USA	Meta-analysis	17 single-case studies	Mixed AAC	Both	Partner instruction significantly improved AAC outcomes, especially for children
Laubscher, Pope, & Light, 2024	USA	Qualitative interviews	Parents of children with ASD (beginning communicators)	Mixed AAC	Caregivers	Parents emphasized AAC as critical to early communication; training essential
Light et al., 2019	USA	State-of-science review	n/a	Technology supports	Gap	Highlighted emerging AAC technologies (VSDs, just-in-time programming) for literacy
Lorang et al., 2023	USA	Survey	376 SLPs in early intervention	Mixed AAC	Teachers	Found AAC commonly recommended but limited literacy integration; training gaps identified
Lund et al., 2017	USA	Qualitative survey/ interviews	AAC specialists	Mixed AAC	Teachers	Identified clinical decision factors in AAC assessment; stressed importance of training
McNaughton et al., 2019	USA	Conceptual/ person-centered framework	n/a	Mixed AAC	Gap	Advocated capacity-building in AAC, including literacy supports for teachers/caregivers
Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024	South Africa	Survey	Special school teachers (n = 124)	Mixed AAC	Teachers	Training improved teacher perceptions of AAC; identified systemic barriers
Nordström et al., 2019	Sweden	Survey (teachers)	54 special educators; 59 students with reading difficulties	Assistive technology apps (TTS/STT)	Teachers	Apps increased access to text; variability in student outcomes; highlighted training need
Parsons et al., 2017	Australia	Systematic review	7 studies (remote training for parents of children with ASD)	Mixed AAC	Caregivers	Remote parent-mediated training feasible; improved parent knowledge and child communication
Roldán et al., 2021	Spain/USA	Observational case study	1 child with CCN + parents	High-tech AAC	Caregivers	Emotional conversations

Table 1 (continued)

Author, Year	Country	Study Design	Sample (n, age)	AAC Type	Training Focus	Main Outcomes
						supported with AAC; caregiver training enhanced outcomes
Serret et al., 2017	France	Exploratory intervention	Minimally verbal children with ASD (n = 25, 6–12y)	Serious game (SEMA-TIC)	Gap	Improved alphabet knowledge, decoding, and sentence reading with AAC-supported game
Smith & Hustad, 2016	USA	Survey + longitudinal	26 families of children with CP (early intervention)	Mixed AAC	Caregivers	Expressive language strongest predictor of AAC inclusion; parent perceptions highlighted
Suhr et al., 2023	USA	Observational study	Nonspeaking autistic students (school-age)	High-tech AAC devices	Teachers	Classroom context influenced device use; highlighted training/support needs
Finestack et al., 2022	USA	Scoping review	59 caregiver-implemented communication intervention studies (children 0–48 months)	Mixed AAC	Caregivers	Caregiver-implemented interventions supported child expressive language development; limited evidence for infants <12 months; highlighted need for stronger AAC-focused caregiver training.
Ulriksen et al., 2024	Norway	Multiple single-case study	Students with ID (n = 6, school-age)	Mixed AAC	Teachers	Reading instruction with AAC improved decoding, maintained gains at follow-up
Uthoff et al., 2021	Germany	Focus groups	Stakeholders (clinicians, educators, caregivers)	Mixed AAC	Both	Collaboration barriers (insurance delays, AAC knowledge gaps); highlighted role of training centers
van der Schuit et al., 2010	Netherlands	Quasi-experimental	Children with ID (n = 20, 6–12y)	Immersive AAC communication	Teachers	AAC intervention improved communication/engagement; literacy outcomes limited
Walker & Snell, 2013	USA	Meta-analysis	54 single-case studies	Mixed AAC	Gap	AAC reduced challenging behavior; emphasized training and skill generalization

Table 1 (continued)

Author, Year	Country	Study Design	Sample (n, age)	AAC Type	Training Focus	Main Outcomes
Quinn et al., 2020	USA	Quasi-experimental	Parents of children with CCN (n = 18, preschool)	AAC-supported dialogic reading	Caregivers	Parent training increased child engagement and comprehension
Costantino & Bonati, 2014	Italy	Scoping review	14 RCTs/interventions supplementing spoken communication (children)	Mixed AAC (aided/unaided)	Gap	AAC/interventions can supplement speech; methodological gaps; implications for literacy supports
Gona et al., 2014	Kenya	Qualitative (caregiver interviews)	10 caregivers in rural settings	Low-tech AAC	Caregivers	Parents reported AAC improved communication; emphasized training relevance in low-resource contexts
Berenguer, Martínez, De Stasio, & Baixauli, 2022	Spain/Italy	Systematic review & qualitative meta-synthesis	19 studies (297 parents of AAC users, ages varied)	Mixed AAC	Caregivers	Parents valued AAC for enhancing participation, but identified barriers such as training gaps, costs, and difficulties integrating AAC across contexts.
Didion, Toste, & Filderman, 2019	USA	Meta-analysis	28 teacher professional development (PD) studies (elementary–secondary students)	Gap (general literacy PD, not AAC-specific)	Teachers	Teacher PD significantly improved student reading outcomes, particularly for code-focused skills; provides evidence base for AAC-related teacher training.
Beaudoin, Sébire, & Couture, 2014	Canada	Systematic review	Toddlers with ASD, parent training interventions	Mixed AAC	Caregivers	Parent training improved caregiver use of AAC strategies; children showed variable but generally positive communication outcomes
Almubark, Spencer, & Foster, 2025	Saudi Arabia/USA	Narrative intervention (multiple baseline)	Children with autism (n = 3, school-aged)	Mixed AAC	Both	First empirical test of narrative-based AAC intervention; showed feasibility and improvements in story retell and comprehension

Note. AAC = Augmentative and Alternative Communication; CP = cerebral palsy; DHH = deaf and hard of hearing; ID = intellectual disability; SSMI = severe speech and motor impairments; VOCA = voice output communication aid. “Training focus” refers to the primary target population for communication partner instruction (caregivers, teachers, both, or identified as a gap in the literature). Studies are listed in no particular order.

Annex C

Table 2.

Outcomes of AAC-Supported Literacy Interventions by Theme

Theme	Key Studies	Evidence Summary
Emergent literacy (phonological awareness, decoding, letter–sound)	Caron et al., 2023; Holyfield et al., 2025; Ulriksen et al., 2024; Serret et al., 2017	Explicit literacy instruction with embedded AAC supports improved letter–sound correspondence, decoding, and early word reading.
Shared reading and vocabulary	Binger et al., 2008; Kent-Walsh et al., 2010; Cox et al., 2015; Fäldt et al., 2019; Quinn et al., 2020; Gormley et al., 2020	Caregiver coaching and teacher-supported shared reading increased multi-symbol messages, vocabulary use, and engagement; gains generalized to daily routines.
Reading comprehension / narrative	Conroy et al., 2019; Quinn et al., 2020; Almubark et al., 2025	AAC-supported dialogic/narrative interventions improved comprehension, sequencing, and story retell.
Generalization of literacy/communication skills	Cox et al., 2015; Gormley et al., 2020; Fäldt et al., 2019; Gona et al., 2014	Skills acquired in structured AAC literacy tasks generalized to home and classroom environments; caregivers reported improved participation.
Teacher training and perceptions	Andzik et al., 2017; Andzik et al., 2018; Lorang et al., 2023; Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024; Lund et al., 2017; Conlon et al., 2021; Didion et al., 2019	Teachers and SLPs recognized value of AAC for literacy but reported training gaps; professional development was linked to improved practice and student outcomes.
Caregiver training and experiences	Beaudoin et al., 2014; Binger et al., 2008; Kent-Walsh et al., 2010; Laubscher et al., 2024; Berenguer et al., 2022; Finestack et al., 2022; Fäldt et al., 2019; Gona et al., 2014	Parents valued AAC for early participation; training/coaching improved home communication though contextual barriers (time, cost, integration) persisted.
Reviews & conceptual frameworks	Barker et al., 2013; Branson & Demchak, 2011; Douglas, 2012; Kent-Walsh & McNaughton, 2005; Kent-Walsh et al., 2015; Crowe et al., 2021; McNaughton et al., 2019; Light et al., 2019; Costantino & Bonati, 2014	Evidence syntheses and frameworks emphasized partner instruction, technology supports, and capacity-building; identified methodological gaps and training needs.
Classroom context and literacy environments	Benson-Goldberg & Erickson, 2024; Nordström et al., 2019; Suhr et al., 2023; Smith & Hustad, 2016	Studies of classroom context and literacy environments highlighted limited literacy opportunities, variability in assistive technology implementation, and the influence of teacher and environmental factors.
Broader outcomes, collaboration, and behaviour	Brady et al., 2014; Roldán et al., 2021; Uthoff et al., 2021; Walker & Snell, 2013	AAC interventions were associated with improved language outcomes (predictors of vocabulary growth), enhanced emotional communication, greater stakeholder collaboration, and reduced challenging behaviors.

Note. Themes were derived from narrative synthesis of the 45 included studies. AAC = Augmentative and Alternative Communication.

Annex D

Table 3.

Risk of Bias Assessment (JBI Tools): Study-Level Summary (n = 45)

Author, Year	Country	Study Design	JBI Tool	Appraisal (0–1)	Risk Rating	Key Notes
Andzik et al., 2017	USA	Cross-sectional survey	JBI Cross-sectional	0.79	Moderate	Reliable outcomes; confounders not fully addressed
Andzik et al., 2018	USA	Qualitative interviews	JBI Qualitative	0.85	High	Strong methodology and analysis
Conlon, Preston, & Zupan, 2021	Australia	Mixed-methods survey	JBI Cross-sectional / Qual.	0.93	High	Sampling and analysis well-reported
Barker et al., 2013	USA	Narrative/c onceptual	JBI Textual	0.82	Moderate	Non-empirical; clear rationale
Benson-Goldberg & Erickson, 2024	USA	Observational / case series	JBI Case Series	0.71	Moderate	Consistent methods; clear outcomes
Binger et al., 2008	USA	Single-case multiple probe	JBI Case Series / SCED	0.85	High	Fidelity and repeated measures reported
Brady et al., 2014	USA	Cohort (longitudinal SEM)	JBI Cohort	0.72	Moderate	Predictor-focused; some confounding limits
Branson & Demchak, 2011	USA	Systematic review	JBI SR/Syntheses	0.95	Moderate	Variable quality of included studies
Caron et al., 2023	USA	Single-case experimental	JBI Case Series / SCED	0.85	High	Strong design; explicit outcomes
Conroy et al., 2019	USA	Quasi-experimental	JBI Quasi-experimental	0.85	High	Clear comparison; appropriate analyses
Crowe et al., 2021	USA	Umbrella review (mega-review)	JBI SR/ Synthesis	0.86	High	Transparent methods; broad coverage
Cox et al., 2015	USA	Multiple-baseline	JBI Case Series / SCED	0.71	Moderate	Generalization assessed; small n
Douglas, 2012	USA	Narrative/ literature review	JBI Textual	0.94	High	Model guidance; non-empirical
Fäldt et al., 2019	Sweden	Qualitative	JBI Qualitative	0.85	High	Trustworthiness and reflexivity documented
Gormley et al., 2020	USA	Mixed-methods pilot / case	JBI Case Report	0.88	High	Comprehensive case detail
Holyfield et al., 2025	USA	Single-case experimental	JBI Case Series / SCED	0.75	Moderate	Feasibility focus; small n

Table 3 (continued)

Author, Year	Country	Study Design	JBI Tool	Appraisal (0–1)	Risk Rating	Key Notes
Holmer et al., 2017	Sweden	Quasi-experimental (crossover)	JBI Quasi-experimental	0.97	High	Internal validity strong
Ibrahim et al., 2023	UK	Ethnographic qualitative	JBI Qualitative	0.85	High	Thick description; analytic rigor
Kent-Walsh & McNaughton, 2005	USA	Narrative/conceptual	JBI Textual	1.00	High	Partner instruction framework; non-empirical
Kent-Walsh, Binger, & Hasham, 2010	USA	Single-case multiple probe	JBI Case Series / SCED	0.85	High	Fidelity, repeated measures, clear effect
Kent-Walsh, Murza, Malani, & Binger, 2015	USA	Meta-analysis	JBI SR/Synthesis	0.91	High	Consistent effects; transparent methods
Laubscher, Pope, & Light, 2024	USA	Qualitative interviews	JBI Qualitative	0.85	High	Clear methodology and coding
Light et al., 2019	USA	State-of-science review	JBI Textual	0.94	High	Strong synthesis of technologies
Lorang et al., 2023	USA	Survey	JBI Cross-sectional	0.79	Moderate	Sampling constraints; reliable outcomes
Lund et al., 2017	USA	Qualitative survey/interviews	JBI Qualitative	0.85	High	Credibility present; transferability limited
McNaughton et al., 2019	USA	Conceptual/person-centered	JBI Textual	1.00	High	Practice implications explicit
Ngcobo & Bornman, 2024	South Africa	Survey	JBI Cross-sectional	0.94	High	Strong design and analyses
Nordström et al., 2019	Sweden	Survey (teachers)	JBI Cross-sectional	0.94	High	Clear measures; appropriate statistics
Parsons et al., 2017	Australia	Systematic review	JBI SR/Syntheses	0.86	High	Remote parent-mediated training synthesis
Roldán et al., 2021	Spain/USA	Case report	JBI Case Report	0.88	High	Intervention and outcomes clearly reported
Serret et al., 2017	France	Exploratory intervention	JBI Quasi-experimental	0.94	High	Pre-post gains; appropriate measures
Smith & Hustad, 2016	USA	Survey + longitudinal	JBI Cross-sectional / Cohort	0.71	Moderate	Parent report + follow-up; some limits
Suhr et al., 2023	USA	Observational study	JBI Cross-sectional	0.79	Moderate	Contextual insights; non-experimental

Table 3 (continued)

Author, Year	Country	Study Design	JBI Tool	Appraisal (0–1)	Risk Rating	Key Notes
Finestack et al., 2022	USA	Scoping review	JBI SR/Syntheses	0.91	High	Broad inclusion; variable primary study quality
Ulriksen et al., 2024	Norway	Multiple single-case	JBI Case Series / SCED	0.80	Moderate	Maintenance assessed; small n
Uthoff et al., 2021	Germany	Qualitative focus groups	JBI Qualitative	0.85	High	Stakeholder triangulation; strong rigor
van der Schuit et al., 2010	Netherlands	Quasi-experimental	JBI Quasi-experimental	1.00	High	Improvement found; literacy outcomes limited
Walker & Snell, 2013	USA	Meta-analysis	JBI SR/Syntheses	1.00	High	Consistent findings; robust synthesis
Quinn et al., 2020	USA	Quasi-experimental	JBI Quasi-experimental	0.85	High	Parent training effect on engagement/comprehension
Costantino & Bonati, 2014	Italy	Scoping review	JBI SR/Syntheses	0.91	High	Methodological limitations in included RCTs
Gona et al., 2014	Kenya	Qualitative (caregiver interviews)	JBI Qualitative	0.85	High	Trustworthiness established; contextual constraints
Berenguer et al., 2022	Spain/Italy	Systematic review & meta-synthesis	JBI SR/Syntheses	0.91	High	Parent perspectives synthesized; limitations in primary studies
Didion, Toste, & Filderman, 2019	USA	Meta-analysis	JBI SR/Syntheses	0.95	High	PD effects significant; rigorous methods
Beaudoin, Sébire, & Couture, 2014	Canada	Systematic review	JBI SR/Syntheses	0.82	Moderate	Mixed outcomes; transparent synthesis
Almubark, Spencer, & Foster, 2025	Saudi Arabia/USA	Single-case (multiple baseline)	JBI Case Series / SCED	0.85	High	Feasibility; small n, promising effects

Note. Risk of bias was assessed using Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal Tools appropriate to each study design. “Appraisal (0–1)” is left blank for your exact numeric scores from your completed JBI coding; “Risk Rating” reflects the qualitative interpretation (High ≥ 0.85 ; Moderate 0.70–0.84; Low 0.50–0.69; Critically Low < 0.50).

Annex E

Figure 2.

JBI Appraisal Checklist – Analytical Cross-Sectional Studies

Annex F

Figure 3.

JB I Appraisal Checklist – Systematic Reviews & Research Syntheses

Annex G

Figure 4.

JBI Appraisal Checklist – Case Series

Annex H

Figure 5.

JBI Appraisal Checklist – Case Reports

Annex I

Figure 6.

JBI Appraisal Checklist – Cohort Studies

Annex J

Figure 7.

JBI Appraisal Checklist – Narrative/Textual Evidence

Annex K

Figure 8.

JBI Appraisal Checklist – Quasi-Experimental Studies

Annex L

Figure 9.

JBI Appraisal Checklist – Qualitative Research

